

Simplified overview of ecological groups and the most common earthworms in arable fields

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Ecological groups

Legend:

Litter dweller	Epigeic
Deep burrower	Anecic
Small shallow burrower	Endogeic
Larger shallow burrower	Endogeic

Species – Scheme

Figure: Kevin Butt

Endogeic

Anecic

Endogeic

Epigeic

Adult endogeic earthworms

Endogeic

- pale, pinkish, greyish, greenish colour without pigmentation
- Living mostly in the first 30 cm of the soil

Adult

- “Saddle”, the ring around the body
 - Can be big and swollen or small and flat

Allolobophora chlorotica

Octolasion cyaneum

Aporrectodea rosea

Allolobophora chlorotica

Epigeic earthworms

Adult

- You can find them in your soil block by hand-searching
- Living in first couple of cm in the soil
 - Depend very much on soil moisture
 - “Undisturbed” soil, mulch layer
- Usually smaller than the anecic earthworms (half the size)
- They look very similar to anecic worms when they are juveniles
 - Same size, same colour and sharing the first cm of the soil
- Count them as *Lumbricus spp.* juveniles

Adult =

Photos by Stefanie Krück.
Key to German earthworms.

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Anecic earthworms

Adult

- Coming up with the mustard application
- Depend on “undisturbed” soil
- Sometimes also in the spade sample, but usually disappearing before you can excavate your soil block
- juvenile *L. terrestris* are living as epigeic worms
 - Put them in the column *Lumbricus spp.* juvenile

Colour gradient

Anecic earthworms

Anecic

- with pigmentation, dark, brownish
- Colour gradient from head to tail
- Deep borrower probably coming up with the mustard application

Adult

- “Saddle”, the ring around the body towards the end of the head
 - Can be big and swollen or small and flat, but usually different in colour

Juvenile

- No saddle
- Size is not an indication for being juvenile or adult
- It is hard to determine juveniles for their ecological groups
- Because juvenile *L. terrestris* are living as epigeic worms
 - Put them in the column *Lumbricus spp.* juvenile

Lumbricus terrestris, hatchlings

Lumbricus terrestris, juvenile

